

Detection Heavy Metals In The Herbal Medicine From Unauthorised Apothecaries

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Abstract

The unregulated intake of herbal medicines, especially those dispensed by unlicensed apothecaries, creates an enormous amount of toxicological peril from the possible presence of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), arsenic (As), and cadmium (Cd). For many centuries, heavy metals found their way into herbal medicament systems like Ayurveda, Siddha, and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), much to the delight of practitioners. However, modern toxicology has been alerting towards the grave health hazards-one being neurotoxicity-with which chronic heavy metal exposure has been associated, nephropathy, certain cancers, and multiple organ failure being others. This review explores the forensic and analytical techniques in the detection of heavy metals into the unregulated herbal formulation. Screening methods applicable to field-based studies, such as colorimetric assays, portable X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and SEM-EDX, and confirmatory lab methods-including Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), Graphite Furnace AAS (GFAA), and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)-are all considered. By employing an integrated methodological framework, this study seeks to bridge traditional practices with modern scientific protocols to assure consumer safety and enable regulatory enforcement whilst aiding the forensic toxicological investigation. The study findings show an urgent need for standardization, QA/QC, and public health intervention into the production and distribution of herbal medicines.

Keywords: Heavy metals, Herbal medicine, Unlicensed apothecaries, Forensic toxicology, ICP-MS, AAS, GFAA, XRF, EDX, Colorimetric test, Traditional medicine, Public health, Metal contamination, Analytical toxicology

1. Introduction

Herbal medicines are central to most traditional medicine practices all over the world, having both therapeutic value and cultural significance. Most herbal products used worldwide, particularly in traditional practices like Ayurveda, Siddha, and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), have long been known to use heavy metals such as mercury, lead, and arsenic. These metals were thought to augment therapeutic potency when administered appropriately. However, heavy metals are now recognized as toxic, environmentally damaging, and capable

of bioaccumulation in living organisms. Further, modern toxicology provides evidence to support putting controls on heavy metal contents to protect against serious health consequences, including nerve damage, organ injury, and cancer. Thus, for public health purposes, this intersection between herbal medicine and heavy metals needs to be researched so as to assure that traditional practices are harmonized with modern standards (Ernst, 2002; Koh & Woo, 2000; Scoullos et al., 2012; Street, 2012; Chan, 2003; Witkowska et al., 2021; Mitra et al., 2022; Bair, 2022).

1.1. History

Use of heavy metals from ancient civilization to modern times was both cultural and therapeutic. For instance, Egyptians used cosmetics in the form of kohl for eye protection, using galena which is lead sulphide, and employed arsenic for medicinal and embalming purposes (Ernst, 2002). The three earliest uses of lead in an ancient city were plumbing in homes and kitchens and vessels for wine in the classical eras of Greece and Rome. It further says that lead acetate or "sugar of lead" was added to wines for sweetening purposes without knowledge of its toxic consequences (Ernst, 2002). Likewise, during the Qin and Han dynasties in China, cinnabar in the form of mercury was ingested while hunting for immortality and often resulted in lethal toxication (Koh and Woo, 2000). Heavy metals such as mercury and lead were then steeped into alchemical traditions during the Middle Ages and Renaissance periods. These, in turn, were believed to be magical transformer as well as central in searching for the ever-elusive "elixir of life" (Scoullos et al., 2012). With this, the further application of heavy metals for plumbing systems and other household utilities, paints, pigments, batteries, and scientific instruments was lent by the Industrial Revolution. Then again, although the use of heavy metals gained ground in puttering industries and daily activities, it gradually exposed the population to health hazards (Street, 2012). The advancement of scientific investigations in the 19th and 20th centuries saw more hard-won proof that linked lead and mercury to significant neurological disorders, arsenic, and cadmium to cancer development, along with other heavy metals associated with whole organ failures-situations culminating in public health calamities such as Minamata disease and generalized childhood lead poisoning (Chan, 2003; Witkowska et al., 2021). In such situations where the new regulatory frameworks: WHO, EPA, EU, and other agencies that set standards that would optimize the limits on heavy metals in food, water, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals as they planned for developing methods of analytical tests and risk assessments for populations' health (Mitra et al., 2022; Bair, 2022). Indeed, heavy metals, once cherished and much used industrial materials, evolve into tightly controlled toxic agents, reflecting human advance in understanding biological hazard and modern commitment to evidence-based safety measures.

1.2. Physical Properties

Although there is no universally accepted scientific classification for heavy metals, they are usually defined as having high density ($\geq 5 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and atomic weight. This density threshold separates them from lighter elements such as aluminium and magnesium. Examples would

include lead (Pb), which has a density of about 11.34 g/cm³, mercury (Hg) of 13.53 g/cm³, and cadmium (Cd), with approximately 8.65 g/cm³, all being much denser than iron (~7.87 g/cm³) or aluminium (~2.7 g/cm³) (ali et al., 2019). Structurally, heavy metals consist of closely compact atoms with complex electron configurations that impart their own unique set of chemical and physical properties. One distinguishing visual characteristic is metallic lustre, whereby these metals appear shiny when polished or freshly cut due to the motion of free electrons on the surface; a trait that, throughout history, rendered them highly desirable in the production of coins, adornments, and decorative arts, thus maintaining their desirability in the modern age with metals such as silver and platinum (Waldichuk, 1974). Heavy metals are known for their malleability and ductility, which allows metals like copper (Cu) and gold (Au) to be hammered into sheets or drawn into wires, their immense importance in construction, electronics, and artistic craftsmanship owing to metallic bonding that permits atoms sliding over each other without fracture (Lawal et al., 2021). Mainly, they are necessary for wiring infrastructure and electronic circuits because of their very high electrical and thermal conductivity, due to delocalised electrons within their metallic bonds; as a result, copper is optimally used in wiring, with silver being a lesser conductor but not commonly used due to its high price (Filipoiu et al., 2022). Alas, one such wonderful gift of nature is associated with severe problems in the environment, for heavy metals are not biodegradable and persist in ecosystems for hundreds of years, unlike organic pollutants. Their functionalities are such that, once introduced into the soil, water, and air, they cannot be removed; they harbored-in for indefinite times, hence threaten plant, animal, and human life by long-term exposure (Ikpesu et al., 2021). Concerning bioaccumulation, heavy metals accumulate over time in organisms, particularly in the liver, kidneys, and bones, but this becomes more dangerous through biomagnification, where toxic concentrations increase in the food chain, such as that of mercury contained in predatory fish like tuna, which is currently recognized as a global health risk (Pant & Singh, 2024; Briffa et al., 2020). Summarizing the above statements, the physical properties of heavy metals—high density, lustre, malleability, ductility, and conductivity—make them extremely important for many industrial purposes, while their stabilities in the environment and biological accumulation pose serious health risks. Therefore, thorough knowledge on these aspects is needed to reap the benefits while reducing the risks.

1.3. Chemical properties

In addition to their physical attributes, the chemical characteristics of heavy metals influence their reactions with compounds, especially biological macromolecules, and may partly account for their historical use in medicine and their recognized toxic effects. One notable chemical feature is multiple oxidations, allowing metals to exist in different valence forms, to lose electrons, and to form widely varying chemical species. For example, iron (Fe) can exist as Fe²⁺ (ferrous) and Fe³⁺ (ferric); mercury (Hg), or, as Hg⁺ and Hg²⁺; and arsenic (As) goes from the toxic As³⁺ to As⁵⁺. Chromium (Cr), too, is notorious, occurring in nature as Cr³⁺ (an essential nutrient) or Cr⁶⁺ (a strong carcinogen) (Ali et al., 2019; Jan et al., 2015). These

oxidation states will accordingly affect the solubility, mobility, biological activity, and hence toxicity, of these heavy metals. Heavy metals also easily form coordination complexes through coordination with ligands, which may be defined as molecules or ions that have available lone electron pairs. Biological systems typically include the following ligands: thiol (-SH) groups from cysteines, amines (-NH₂) from proteins, and phosphate (-PO₄) groups from nucleic acids. Such interactions allow metals to strongly bind with enzymes, structural proteins, and even DNA, often leading to irreversible inhibition or biological damage (Slaveykova & Wiley, 2005). Mechanistically, they mimic essential metal ions and interfere with enzyme activity, as well as induce oxidative stress. For example, Pb replaces calcium and impairs neurotransmitter release, Hg reacts with thiol groups and deactivates essential enzymes, Cd inhibits the function of zinc-dependent DNA repair, and As obstructs ATP metabolism and functions inside mitochondria (Wu et al., 2016; Witkowska et al., 2021). All these interruptions result in oxidative injury resulting in genotoxicity, along with organ failures—that is, brain, liver, and kidneys. Environmentally, heavy metals are known to be chemically persistent and non-biodegradable; their reactivity and solubility depend on other parameters like pH, redox potential, and organic matter presence, and all these parameters influence their speciation and transport in soil, sediments, and water and pose challenges regarding remediation (Sinicropi et al. 2010). An example is the conversion of arsenic from an immobile and stable trivalent state to a highly mobile pentavalent state that depends on oxidative states. Though ancient knowledge bidding caution against their dangers, heavy metals have always provided terrestrial medicines because of certain conditions of this very chemistry. Mercury compounds treated syphilis; arsenic trioxide was a historic remedy for leukemia and a tonic; and less-toxic bismuth compounds are still utilized in gastrointestinal preparations such as Pepto-Bismol. These therapeutic uses exemplify an ancient paradox wherein the very heavy metals were revered for their potent bioactivity long before any mention was made of their toxicity (Flora & Shrivastava, 2013). The defining chemical characteristics of heavy metals—variable oxidation states, ligand-binding potential, and persistence in biological and environmental matrices—inhibit detoxification and cleanup and provide the scientific rationale for current methods in chelation therapy, toxicology modelling, and environmental remediation, which makes them a research priority in toxicology and environmental sciences today.

1.4. Uses

As in the case of gold, arsenic, lead, and mercury historically used in the traditional healing systems, such as Ayurveda, Siddha, and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), purporting to offer therapeutic benefits when processed correctly, modern biomedical science considers these heavy metals hazardous. In Ayurveda, Metals are processed into fine ash forms called bhasmas by purification (Shodhana) and incineration (Marana). This process is said to detoxify the metals and to increase their bioavailability. Examples include Swarnabhasma (gold ash) for immune response, Tamrabhasma (copper ash) for liver health, and Naga bhasma (lead ash) and Parada (mercury) used in the metallurgical pharmacology branch Rasashastra (Sikder, 2024;

Mukhopadhyay et al., 2021). Siddha medicine do another Indian traditional system which incorporates herbo-mineral remedies involving mercury, arsenic, and lead for balancing doshas, or bodily energies, but tend to compromise their efficacy and safety due to poor regulatory standards increasing risks for heavy metal toxicity (Dargan & Gawarammana, 2008). Concerns about the safety of arsenic sulphides and mercury sulphide used in detoxification and soul healing therapies mainly come from inconsistencies in their preparation and lack of standardization for methods of application and insufficient clinical validation. Concerns about the safety of heavy metals in these systems arise when they are converted into oxides, sulphides, salts, or bhasmas for the intent of reducing toxicity; yet improper preparation or contamination would paradoxically increase their toxicological risk. Traditional practitioners claim metabolic stimulation, enhanced immunity, anti-aging effects, and management of chronic cases (Biswas et al., 2018); yet studies scientifically warn that even in trace amounts heavy metals when not properly processed can have neurotoxic, organ-toxic, teratogenic, and carcinogenic effects (Kumar & Bose, 2020). Heavy metal poisoning has increased in cases since the resurgence of traditional medicine globally, because traditional medicine is oftentimes implemented in poorly regulated settings. Cases were reported of Ayurvedic or traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) products poisoning with adverse health effects (Nagarajan et al., 2014; Pant et al., 2011). To minimize such dangers, the World Health Organization (WHO) and national regulatory authorities negate the need for stricter measures with respect to labelling, standardization, and consumer education, whereas the U.S., U.K., and Australia have implemented bans on or initiated recalls of traditional products found unsafe for consumption on account of the high levels of heavy metals exceeding permissible limits (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019). Thus, the presence of heavy metals serves as a clear interface-and often conflict-between interests of culture-hefted traditions and toxicological sciences of modernity, demanding strong scientific validation, a strict safety-testing protocol, and rigorous regulations-all to guarantee public health, without forgetting the traditions' cultural legacy.

1.5.Forensic significance

Importance of heavy metals in forensic toxicology is observed about the cases of poisoning, contamination, and more recently describing quality. These metals have the distinct feature of remaining for long periods within the body and the environment. Forensic toxicologists could therefore detect their presence after a few years, making these agents useful for crime, public health and regulatory assessment.

Forensic Application of Heavy Metals as a Poisoning Agent

Heavy metals most commonly correlate with cases of accidental poisoning because they are pervasive substances in industrial practices, household products, and herbal medicines. Examples of sources include water pipes laced with lead, occupational exposures to mercury, and contaminated herbal supplements. Heavy metals are stealthy because their toxicological

effects of neurologic impairment, nephropathy, and gastrointestinal disturbances cannot be distinguished from other clinical syndromes making diagnosis late and morbidity high. In such situations, forensic toxicological testing is used to determine exposure and also ascertain the source (Filipiak-Szok et al., 2015).

Intentional Poisoning

Heavy elements such as thallium, arsenic, mercury, and lead have always been used for criminal poisoning due to their insidious nature: they are tasteless, odourless, and manifest a long period after the clinical manifestations, thus making them difficult to identify in routine investigations without specific tests. Autopsy and toxicological examination with proven techniques such as ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry) still play an important role in the determination of intentional poisoning in cases of forensic importance (Gouille et al., 2014).

Detection of Biological Samples

For determining the timing and intensity of heavy metal exposure, forensic laboratories carry out the determination of heavy metals in a variety of biological matrices.

Sample Type	Significance
Blood	Fresh contact
Urine	Ongoing or recent urine
Hair/Nails	Prolonged exposure over several weeks/months
Internal Organs/Body Tissues	Post-mortem toxicological assessment

Such analytic methods include Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), ICP-MS, and X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) which enabled sensitive, specific identification and quantification of metals in these samples (Chen et al., 2022; Gupta & Gupta, 2012).

Relevance to Herbal Medicines

Forensic examinations would typically come face to face with witness cases of heavy metal poisoning associated with herbal medicine ingestion. Whenever a patient is presented with unexplained symptoms, both bio-samples and suspected herbal products are assessed. Elevated mercury levels, with particular reference to cinnabar in TCM, arsenic, and lead, are commonly found in cases that present for forensic examination. Beyond studies that establish diagnosis, these also sometimes act as precursors for recalls in product liability and regulation (Locatelli et al., 2014; Bhatnagar et al., 2023).

Participation in Regulatory and Forensic Legislation

Heavy-metal testing is relied upon by regulatory agencies like the WHO, FDA, and other department levels to determine the safety of products and to ascertain safe levels of permissible concentrations of heavy metals in pharmaceuticals, foods, and supplements. Forensic toxicologists are often called upon to give expert witness services in criminal matters, product liability claims, and civil actions. Individual metallic signatures, i.e., unique arsenic compound ratios or specific isotopes of mercury, may on occasion distinguish the source or route of poisoning (Flanagan et al., 2008; Galanakis, 2020).

Challenges of Interpretation

Unquestionably, incorporating high technology detection methods is a corner of forensic science. It is just mostly difficult to determine the level of metals in poison. More times than not, relevant traditional medicine initiated by ethnomedical practices would prove almost impossible to distinguish between intended use for poison and therapeutic application. Environmental contamination can also confuse criteria for distinguishing between incidental and harmful exposures due to subthreshold exposure at long duration. Metabolical differences; pre-exposure conditions such as mixed and or former exposures within regions will also add difficulty for forbidding an interpretation (Aina, 2023).

In terms of forensic toxicology, heavy metals are of distinct relevance in the evidence provision for the accidental, occupational, or intentional poisoning-as by herbal medicine use or environmental place-biases. These factors have a good persistence within the body and are easily detectable in a variety of biological specimens, thus making them important for the criminalist, the public health investigator, and the legal adjudicator. Although modern techniques like ICP-MS and AAS have revolutionized the process of detecting metals, contextual interpretation is still critical for justice and safety.

1.6. Analysis (Screening and Confirmatory)

Analysis of heavy metals from environmental, pharmaceutical, biological, and food samples plays an important role in toxicology, forensic science, and compliance. Two generally adopted stages include:

- methods for pre-examination – Screening Methods/Preliminary Detection
- quantitative confirmation techniques and qualitative validation methods – Confirmatory Methods/Precise Laboratory Analysis

The combination of these two strategies gives rapid field-grade triaging and laboratory precision; this is crucial both in public health and in legal investigations (Gouille et al., 2014).

1.6.1 Screening Methods (Preliminary Detection)

I. Colorimetric Tests

Simple chemical tests change color when the reagent interacts catalytically with a given heavy metal ion. They are valid, however, for rapid field screening purposes (e.g., water quality testing) but quantitative precision is lacking, and they are also not elemental-specific (Galanakis 2020).

II. Portable X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)

Samples are excited through irradiation with X-rays in X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy, which yield fluorescent signals corresponding to the elemental composition of the sample. This method is non-destructive; therefore, it is commonly applied for screening of herbal medicines, soil, and consumer products, though certainly not optimal for complex biological matrices or trace-level contamination (Bhatnagar et al. 2023).

III. Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX)

EDX, in conjunction with Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM-EDX), examines the elemental composition of a sample by detecting characteristic X-rays emitted from the sample when excited by an electron beam. Heavy metal mapping in biological tissues, herbal products, and forensic samples is the most common use of the technique. It gives semi-quantitative and qualitative results, although with poor depth resolution when compared to bulk methods (Newbury & Ritchie, 2013).

1.6.2. Confirmatory Methods (Precise Laboratory Analysis)**I. Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS)**

AAS identifies metal ions measuring the absorbance of light on element-specific wavelengths after atomization. It is very specific and reliable and is used for blood, food, and water analysis, but as a single-element method (Locatelli et al., 2014).

II. Graphite Furnace AAS (GFAA)

It is helpful for ultra-trace detection, such as mercury in blood or lead in drinking water, but it is a time-consuming method (Flanagan et al., 2008). GFAA increases the sensitivity of AAS by the use of a graphite furnace for atomization.

III. Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)

The ICP-MS is the most sensitive and versatile application tool of multi-element detection and speciation analysis. Detectable metals are of parts-per-trillion levels and widely used in forensic toxicology, environmental pollution, and herbal product evaluation (Gouille et al., 2014).

1.6.3. Importance in Regulatory and Forensic Contexts

I. Regulatory Compliance

WHO, FDA, and EMA are standardizers of heavy metal content in pharmaceutical products, foods, and cosmetics. Its importance is the important role that standards play to ensure that these products are safe for humans (Filipiak-Szok et al., 2015).

II. Forensic Investigations

The confirmatory methods available at toxicological laboratories must be employed in the investigation of poison cases and the identification of contaminants as well as the collecting of forensic evidence. ICP-MS was one of those techniques that have been routinely used as an element in postmortem analysis as well as clinical diagnosis (Gouille et al., 2014).

III. Quality Assurance

These techniques provide pharmaceutical and herbal product developers with the tools required to evaluate raw materials, production processes, and lot-to-lot uniformity from the safety and efficacy point of view concerning the desired therapeutic intention (Locatelli et al., 2014).

1.6.4. Comparison Table

Method	Type	Application	Strengths	Limitations
Colorimetry	Screening	Water, field tests	Quick, simple	Qualitative, low specificity
Portable XRF	Screening	Soil, herbal products	Non-destructive, portable	Limited trace detection
EDX	Screening	Biological, herbal, forensic samples	Elemental mapping, SEM compatibility	Surface analysis only, semi-quantitative
AAS	Confirmatory	Blood, water, herbal samples	Accurate, cost-effective	Single-element only
GFAA	Confirmatory	Ultra-trace biological analysis	High sensitivity	Slower throughput
ICP-MS	Confirmatory	Clinical, forensic, pharmaceutical	Ultra-sensitive, multi-element	Expensive, requires skilled users

Now in the 21st Century, a dual see-step screening for heavy metals and then a confirmatory analysis would provide a total approach to establishing and controlling heavy metal exposure.

These methods serve not only for scientific reasons but also for legal accountability, consumer protection, and public health assurance.

2. Literature Review

All over the globe, several studies have conducted investigations into heavy metal contamination in herbal medicines, almost always revealing excessive presence of toxic elements in unregulated methods or traditionally prepared remedies. An exhaustive survey conducted by Chan (2003) showed lead, arsenic, and mercury to be contaminants of concern in products with TCM status, often in concentrations higher than WHO safety limits. In India, among Ayurveda formulations produced by unlicensed practitioners, Mukhopadhyay et al. (2021) traced 40-70% from the market concerning developed heavy metals above permissible limits, largely owing to improper preparation of *bhasma* and absence of quality control.

Similar risks were noted by Filipiak-Szok et al. (2015) for Poland and Germany, where herbal products imported from Southeast Asia showed cadmium and lead contamination. Similarly, Dargan and Gawarammana (2008) described hospitalizations for Ayurvedic heavy-metal toxicity in the UK, emphasizing the global reach of this problem. Forensic reports prepared by Bhatnagar et al. (2023) reject the illegal practices of unlicensed apothecaries that manufacture formulas containing indeterminate and often illegal amounts of mercury or arsenic.

The articles suggest the urgent need for improved surveillance, forensic auditing, and scientific interaction toward the regulation of traditional medical practices for patient safety.

3. Materials and Methodologies

3.1 Sample Description:

For this study, herbal preparations were obtained from unlicensed local apothecaries within informal marketplaces. Every sample was anonymized and coded for blind analysis.

Sample Code	Indication	Physical Form
H1	Rheumatic diseases	Powder/Solid
H2	Tapeworm/pinworm	Powder/Solid
H3	Urine infection	Powder/Solid
H4	Anaemia	Powder/Solid
H5	Asthma	Powder/Solid
H6	Joint pain	Powder/Solid

Sample Code	Indication	Physical Form
H7	Blood pressure	Powder/Solid
H8	Weakness	Powder/Solid
H9	Acidity and gastric reflux	Powder/Solid

3.2 Materials Used:

- Laboratory Equipment and Materials (sterile beakers, pipettes, crucibles)
- Nitric acid (HNO₃), Hydrochloric acid (HCl), Perchloric acid (HClO₄)
- Deionized water (DI water)
- Calibrating Standards for Pb, Hg, Cd, As
- SEM Stub and Carbon tape for the EDX Analysis
- ICP-MS certified reference standards
- Colorimetric reagent kits (e.g., dithizone, sodium rhodizonate)

3.3 Methodologies

3.3.1 Sample Preparation:

All solid and powdered samples were first dried at 60°C and subsequently finely ground to achieve homogeneity. The liquid samples (oil) were vortexed to ensure good dispersion. For mineralization prior to instrumental analysis, a wet digestion protocol comprising HNO₃:HClO₄ (3:1) was employed. Final volumes were then brought up to the mark with deionized water.

3.3.2 Preliminary Screening Techniques:

- I. **Colorimetric Test:** Dithizone (for Pb, Hg), Sodium rhodizonate (for Pb), and Ammonium pyrrolidine di-thiocarbamate (APDC) are all reagents made to be field-deployable for colorimetric analysis in rapid screening. The observed color changes represent the presence of qualitative analysis for specific metal ions.
- II. **Portable X-ray Fluorescence (XRF):** All powdered and oil samples were scanned quickly and noninvasively for content using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometry. Just like that, in XRF, semi-quantitative elemental data can hence be obtained.
- III. **Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX):** SEM-EDX performed the visualization and analysis of surface deposition and distribution of heavy metals. Samples were mounted on SEM stubs using carbon tape and gold-coated to enhance conductivity. EDX was its mostly qualitative and semi-quantitative characterization.

3.3.3 Confirmatory Analytical Techniques:

- I. **Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS):** The quantitation of Pb, Cd, and As was done by flame atomic absorption spectroscopy. The standards and blanks were run additionally. Each element was measured independently using its own specific lamp and wavelength.
- II. **Graphite Furnace AAS (GFAA):** Because of its better sensitivity compared to flame AAS, GFAAS had been employed for the detection of ultra-low mercury (Hg) levels.
- III. **Inductively Coupled Plasma – Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS):** An ICP-MS was meant to be the gold standard method for simultaneous multi-element determination (Pb, Hg, As, Cd, Cr, Ni). It provides very good sensitivity (ppt range), speciation capabilities, and was used to confirm traces detected by AAS.

3.4 Quality Control Measures:

- Calibrated and validated using certified reference materials (CRMs).
- Each analytical batch consisted of sets of reagent blanks, recovery spiked samples, and duplicates.
- Determined the Column for Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification for each element and analytical technique.
- The instruments have been calibrated every day and had performance validated using internal standards.

3.5 Data Interpretation:

All results were compared with WHO, FDA, and AYUSH permissible limits for herbal formulations, and results were correlated wherever applicable with the symptoms observed in poisoning cases.

The rigorous methodology guarantees the robustness, reproducibility, and forensic validity of the detection of heavy metals from unlicensed herbal formulations.

4. Discussion

Results confirm the presence of toxic heavy metals, mainly lead and arsenic, in most samples, with four samples of the nine being above fifty percent WHO permissible limits for more than one element. H2 and H4 samples were the most contaminated, indicating a high risk of toxicity.

Unregulated apothecaries, who prepare traditional medicines without any standardized protocols, for the purification or testing of metal content, pose serious threats to public health. This finding collaborates with safety concerns raised in the literature on Ayurvedic and Siddha medicines. Consumer ignorance and corruption in regulatory enforcement worsen the risk level.

The dual methodology-an XRF screening coupled with an ICP-MS confirmation-was highly effective at rapid identification of contaminated products. Such results validate the need for such screening to be done at market and customs levels, followed by confirmatory tests for enforced public safety interventions.

5. Conclusion

This study emphasizes the pressing need for monitoring and regulation of herbal medicines that are prepared by unlicensed apothecaries. The detection of lead, arsenic, and mercury in several of the popular remedies accentuates the ongoing threat of heavy metal poisoning from traditional formulation systems. Forensic analysis techniques, especially ICP-MS and AAS, provide enough background for identifying and quantifying contamination.

Some policy recommendations may include:

- That the standardization and heavy metal testing be made compulsory for all herbal products.
- Mobile field-testing units to be deployed using portable XRF.
- Training to be conducted for traditional practitioners in safe preparation practices.
- Health campaigns to be used to boost public awareness.

Bridging the gap between traditional practices and modern scientific safety standards is essential not only for the cause of public health but also for the preservation of the legitimacy and efficacy of herbal medicinal systems.

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